

The climate efficacy of peatland rewetting under high CH₄ emissions

Franziska Koebisch^{1,2}, Anke Günther², Vytas Huth¹, Torsten Sachs³, Stephan Glatzel⁴,
Gerald Jurasinski¹

¹University of Greifswald, Peatland Science

²University of Rostock, Landscape Ecology

³GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences

⁴University of Vienna, Department of Geography and Regional Research

Corresponding author: franziska.koebisch@uni-greifswald.de

Abstract

While peatland rewetting seeks to mitigate emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂), it often leads to emissions of methane (CH₄). The latter can, depending on their magnitude, exert a considerable climate warming effect. The extent to which the interplay between mitigated CO₂ emissions and enhanced CH₄ emissions affects the efficacy of peatland rewetting as a climate protection measure is often debated.

Here, we assess the climate impact of peatland rewetting based on the evolving net radiative forcing (RF) trajectory. Using the example of a temperate fen that turned to a substantial CH₄ source after rewetting, we first identify controls for the variation in CH₄ and CO₂ exchange as main component fluxes of the RF budget. We assess the evolving climate impact based on the quantities of RF emitted through rewetting, the time required to reach climate neutrality, and the time required to reach climate benefits compared to an ongoing drainage scenario obtained from emission factors. Finally, we provide a systematic analysis of the climate impact of peatland rewetting by including published studies into our assessment.

Indeed, most peatlands exert persistent climate warming after rewetting. However, assessing the climate efficacy based on the absolute GHG budget alone neglects the fact that rewetting can mitigate GHG emissions substantially when compared to ongoing drainage. In many cases, such climate benefits can be reached instantly. Even if rewetting produces typical levels of CH₄ emissions and cannot completely halt the net CO₂ source, climate benefits can still occur in societally relevant time scales of few years to decades. On top of this, measures to reduce CH₄ emissions could speed up the achievement of the desired climate effects. Our study highlights the role of peatland rewetting as an essential measure to reduce gross emissions from the LULUCF sector and to contribute to *net zero* by 2050.

Introduction

Peatland rewetting is a common measure to curb high emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) from drainage-based land use (Joosten et al., 2012). Globally, peatlands are primarily drained for forestry or food production and emit 1.5 Gt CO₂-equivalents. While the majority of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions comes from burning fossil fuels, reducing emissions from drained peatlands is an important accompanying measure to achieve our climate targets. In particular, because the GHG emissions of drained peatlands consume 10-41% of the remaining emission budget to maintain global warming below 2°C (Leifeld et al., 2019). Peatland rewetting raises the water level to an extent that limits the availability of oxygen in the peat pore space and thereby halts the aerobic decomposition processes responsible for high CO₂ emissions (Darusman et al., 2023). Provided a rapid recolonization with peatland-typical vegetation, many peatlands turn to net CO₂ sinks after rewetting (Valach et al., 2021). However, the re-establishment of high water levels can also re-initiate high emissions of methane (CH₄) and thus diminish the climate mitigation prospects of rewetting (McNicol et al., 2020).

Assessing the climate efficacy of peatland rewetting is complicated by the difficulty of meaningfully putting into relation the opposing climate effects of increased CH₄ emissions on the one hand, and CO₂ emissions mitigated from drainage on the other. The climate effect that results from the specific different radiative efficiencies and atmospheric lifetimes of the involved GHG can be expressed by the radiative forcing (RF) budget derived from atmospheric perturbation modelling (Frolking et al., 2006, 2011; Günther et al., 2020). The global warming potential (GWP) as the most common index to combine different atmospheric behaviours of GHG in a single metric relates to the RF exerted over a fixed reference period. Reporting activities under the Kyoto Protocol are commonly based on a 100-year reference period (IPCC 2023). The adoption of a fixed reference period provides a common standard to compare the climate effects of different land use activities and is the basis for current accounting schemes. Yet, the rating of the climate effect of peatland rewetting may differ depending on the choice of the reference period, thereby contesting the general validity of the assessment: Under a long-term consideration of, for instance, 500 years, the climate effect of peatland rewetting might be rated more favourably than under 100 or even 20 years (Höper et al. 2008). Apart from that, GWP as metric for the climate effect of peatlands is increasingly under question as it does not account for the continuous emission behaviour inherent to ecosystems (Allen et al., 2018). Mainly, however, the GWP as a snapshot in the RF dynamics cannot resolve the underlying trend and the long-term evolution of the RF trajectory. If only a single year is considered, peatland drainage causing ever-increasing warming could be rated equal to or even better than peatland rewetting which causes a temporary RF peak followed by the continuous progression towards cooling. Assessing the climate impacts of peatland management on the basis of common metrics such as the GWP is necessary to comply with the existing reporting

standards in accounting schemes. An assessment based on the GWP alone, however, risks being incomplete or even distorted and may exacerbate the ambiguity on peatland rewetting.

The magnitude of peatland CH₄ emissions and net CO₂ uptake can vary considerably from site to site, and also over time from year to year (Nugent et al., 2018; Strack & Zuback, 2013). This variation in emission behaviour modulates the characteristic course of the post-rewetting RF trajectory and thereby affects the climate efficacy of peatland rewetting. Successful cases where rewetting reduced CO₂ release whilst, at the same time, increased CH₄ emissions only to moderate levels (usually below 20 g m⁻² yr⁻¹), indicate that these sites could be considered climatically neutral (RF<0) within 6 to 15 years after rewetting (Günther et al., 2016; Nugent et al., 2018; Schrier-Uijl et al., 2014; Wilson, Farrell, et al., 2016). On the other side of the spectrum, there are instances where rewetted peatlands turn into large CH₄ sources after rewetting and thus continue to warm the climate in the longer term: Hemes et al. (2018) report CH₄ emissions up to 85 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ from a variety of rewetted Mediterranean wetlands that turned into significant GHG sources, despite high C sequestration rates. Also, (McNicol et al., 2020) report high CH₄ emissions > 30 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ from rewetted peatlands which offset the cooling potential of concurrent C sequestration. Single studies, such as Augustin & Chojnicki (2008) or Hahn et al. (2015) even report extremely high CH₄ emissions of approx. 260 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ from rewetted temperate fens. The uncertainty arising from the high variation in peatland GHG emission behaviour may lower the confidence in the efficacy of peatland rewetting as a climate protection measure.

Here, we aim for a better understanding of the climate impact of peatland rewetting, and to provide more clarity on the efficacy of peatland rewetting as a climate protection measure. Based on the characteristic course of the RF trajectory as it emerges from the CO₂ and CH₄ emission behaviour, we assess the climate impact of peatland rewetting, explicitly taking into account the uncertainty arising from the temporal variation of GHG exchange. Our climate impact assessment is based on four key metrics derived as distinct features of the RF trajectory such as the curve maximum/integrals/intersections. Among these metrics, *peak net radiative forcing* (peak NRF) and *total net radiative forcing* (total NRF) refer to the change in the Earth's energy budget (in fW m⁻²) caused by the greenhouse gases emitted/absorbed through peatland rewetting. *Switchover time* (Frolking et al., 2006) and *climate pay-off time*, in turn, relate to the time required to reach distinct target marks such as the attainment of climate neutrality or climate benefits compared to ongoing drainage. Basic principles about the post-rewetting emission dynamics of CH₄ and CO₂, and the resulting consequences for the net RF budget and the uncertainty of the aspired climate protection targets are illustrated using the example of a rewetted temperate fen that turned into a substantial source for CH₄ with emissions up to 260 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ measured in the first rewetting year (Hahn et al., 2015a). Further, we provide a more systematic picture of the climate impact of peatland rewetting by expanding our assessment to cases reported in the existing literature.

More specifically, we:

1. illustrate the RF dynamics as it accrues after peatland rewetting and reveal the implications for the intended climate effects using the four key metrics introduced above including their uncertainty. This analysis is based on the example case of a rewetted temperate fen with an 8-year data record of CO₂ and CH₄ emissions. We fed the measured GHG fluxes into an atmospheric perturbation model (see Günther et al., 2020) to illustrate how the combination of post-rewetting CH₄ release and net CO₂ uptake causes the characteristic course of the radiative forcing trajectory. Based on this model, we further assess the consequences of the observed GHG exchange variation for the uncertainty of the climate protection targets aspired by peatland rewetting.
2. explore the possibilities and limits of the climate protection effects achievable through peatland rewetting, drawing on existing literature. To do so, we expand our approach to reported emissions from rewetted peatlands and examine the prevalent range of the assessment metrics introduced above.

Our results will help to clarify the prospects of peatland rewetting as a climate protection measure in the land use sector and highlight the levers for decision-makers and practitioners to optimize action.

Material and Methods

Post-rewetting CO₂ and CH₄ exchange in a temperate fen

The data basis for the investigation of the temporal variation of post-rewetting CO₂ and CH₄ exchange is an eight-year data record from a rewetted temperate fen. The study site is located in NE Germany (latitude 54°12', longitude 12°10') and has been rewetted by permanent flooding in 2010 after forty years of drainage and grassland use (Koebsch et al., 2013). With the exception of 2010, when CH₄ exchange rates were obtained with the closed chamber technique (Hahn et al., 2015), all GHG exchange data were derived with the eddy covariance approach, which constitutes the state-of-the-art-method to continuously track the turbulent transport of energy and matter on ecosystem scale. Measured rates of net ecosystem CO₂ exchange (NEE) were further partitioned into the component fluxes ecosystem respiration (R_{ECO}) and gross ecosystem productivity (GEP) by empirical modelling. By convention, gas release to the atmosphere (i.e., R_{ECO}) is here denoted with a positive sign.

Controls for the interannual variation of the exchange of NEE, R_{ECO}, GEP and CH₄ were identified based on backward selection approach with linear regression. We interpreted the fitted model coefficients to infer the effect strength and the prevailing response rates for each of the fluxes. As potential drivers, we tested a range of meteorological variables obtained from our own measurements, partly complemented with data from a nearby station of the German Weather Service

(DWD,cdc.dwd.de/portal/Stations-ID: 4271). In addition, we tested the enhanced vegetation index (EVI) derived from MODIS as a potential driver. The EVI constitutes a proxy for plant phenology and vegetation coverage (Huete et al., 2002) and was implemented as a 500x500m pixel value congruent with the eddy covariance flux climatology (Beyer et al., 2021). Refer to Beyer et al. (2021) and Koebisch et al. (2020) for more details on the study site, measurement design, and data processing.

Radiative forcing modelling

We processed the RF [W m^{-2}] dynamics that accrue from the net CO₂ uptake and CH₄ exchange observed in our example study site. We also processed a reference RF trajectory for the scenario of ongoing peatland drainage obtained from drainage emission factors. In this case, N₂O emissions were taken into account in addition to CO₂ and CH₄. We did not include N₂O emissions for the rewetting case, since we consider the evasion of N₂O through incomplete denitrification processes under anaerobic conditions negligible (Hendriks et al., 2007; Wilson et al., 2013, 2022). In a final step, we expanded this approach to incorporate post-rewetting CO₂ and CH₄ exchange rates from other peatlands reported in the literature.

RF is a quantity to describe the change in the Earth's energy budget due to biogeochemical causes (i.e., variations in atmospheric concentrations of greenhouse gasses or aerosols) or biophysical causes (i.e., variations in surface reflectance properties). The addition of CO₂, CH₄ or N₂O from peatlands to the atmosphere contributes to a higher retention of thermal energy (i.e., 'adds' energy to the Earth's heat budget) and, following the common sign convention, will result in a positive RF. We did not include the RF exerted through a change in albedo, although it may be worth being included in future studies (Worrall et al., 2022). In RF modelling, a greenhouse gas flux is noted as a small pulse perturbation of the atmospheric composition described through a first-order decay in atmospheric gas concentration under the simplified assumption of constant lifetimes and constant radiative efficiencies (Joos et al. 2013). For our model, we assume a perfectly mixed atmosphere without any feedback mechanisms (Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change, 2014). Atmospheric perturbations resulting from peatland CO₂ uptake or release were modelled as the composition of five first-order decay pools representing different Earth system reservoirs with specific flux fractions and perturbation lifetimes (Joos et al., 2013). Likewise, atmospheric perturbations resulting from peatland CH₄ emissions were modelled as a first-order decay process of a single pool, yet under consideration of indirect effects such as the impact of varying CH₄ concentrations on ozone and stratospheric water vapor. As the proportion of ancient CH₄ (produced from old peat C, rather than from recent C substrates formed after rewetting) may be substantial in some cases (McNicol et al., 2020), we conservatively included the climate effect of CO₂ from CH₄ oxidation (Günther et al., 2020).

For the rewetting case, the model is set up using annual budgets of CO₂ and CH₄ measured at the study site from 2010 to 2017. Forecasting for the time after 2017 was based on the extrapolation of the mean annual emissions. In order to assess the effect of the interannual flux variation on the shape of the RF trajectory and the deduced key metrics, we estimated the 95% confidence intervals using a bootstrap algorithm with 100 iterations. This bootstrap-based forecasting approach accounts for the uncertainty of the emission forecast, under the assumption that future emissions will remain in the range of the variation observed during the stationary phase of our study period. We omitted the high emissions observed in 2010 from the resampling procedure, as these were caused by vegetation dieback as a direct response to the rapid water level increase (Hahn et al., 2015a). Such an initial CH₄ emission peak can occur frequently after peatland rewetting. However, it is commonly limited to the initial rewetting phase (Beyer et al., 2021) and should therefore not be extrapolated to longer periods of time

The RF reference model for the scenario of ongoing drainage was set up with emission factors (EF) reported from drained grassland, which presents the dominant land use category on peat in Germany and was also the historic land use form at the example study site. EFs were calculated according to the German National inventory approach (Tiemeyer et al., 2020) for a mean annual water level of 52 cm below the surface which reflects the typical drainage situation of grassland on peat (Bechthold et al. 2014). The EF obtained for CO₂ accounted for 9.98 t CO₂-C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ and included on-site emissions, C export through harvest, and off-site CO₂ emissions through DOC loss in ditches (0.31 t DOC ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, IPCC 2014). The CH₄ EF was 15.8 kg CH₄ ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ and included on-site as well as ditch emissions. For N₂O, the EF amounted to 4.6 kg N₂O-N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ and covered emissions from peat mineralization.

The four key metrics introduced to assess the climate protection efficacy of peatland rewetting were derived as distinct features of the NRF curves:

- **peak NRF**, i.e. the maximum climate warming exerted during the rewetting phase [fW m⁻²] before the decline of NRF sets in, was derived from the maximum of the rewetting RF curve. .
- **total NRF** , i.e. the warming effect accumulated during the rewetting phase until the peatland eventually reaches climate neutrality [fW m⁻²]. Total NRF was derived from the integral in the positive section of the rewetting RF curve.
- **switchover time**, i.e., the time when the NRF trajectory approaches zero and the peatland becomes climatically neutral. The switchover time was derived from the intersection of the rewetting RF curve with the time axis and marks the switch from positive to negative NRF, i.e. from net warming to net cooling (Frolking et al., 2006).
- **climate pay-off time**, i.e., the time when rewetting becomes climatically beneficial compared to ongoing drainage as a reference for a business-as-usual land use scenario.

The climate pay-off time was derived from the intersection of the rewetting RF curve with the drainage RF curve. Whilst the previous metrics are constrained to cases where rewetting creates net C sinks (i.e. the stoichiometric ratio between sequestered CO₂-C and released CH₄-C > 1), the climate pay-off time is defined for any cases provided that GHG mitigation in comparison to drainage is achieved.

Literature review

For a more generalized analysis of the climate efficacy of peatland rewetting, we expanded our assessment to the existing literature. As a starting point, we used the survey of Wilson, Blain, et al., (2016), who collated existing peatland rewetting studies as an update of the tier 1 emission factors of the IPCC Wetlands supplement. This collection was further supplemented by studies published after 2016. In order to tailor the data set to the requirements of our study, we imposed additional selection criteria to those raised by Wilson, Blain, et al. (2016):

- both, CO₂ and CH₄ emissions must be available for a site, as the RF modelling is based on the site-specific proportion of both fluxes.
- studied peatlands must have a drainage and rewetting history. We omitted pristine sites as they may differ in major ecological features, such as vegetation, hydrology and geochemistry from their rewetted counterparts with a drainage history (Kreyling et al., 2021).
- CO₂ and CH₄ emissions must be reported at the ecosystem level. Emissions must therefore either have been measured directly on an ecosystem scale using the eddy covariance approach or must have been upscaled accordingly from point-scale chamber measurements.
- mean annual water level (MAWL) must be at least 30 cm below ground. This excludes peatlands that are technically deemed abandoned and/or restored, but do not meet the hydrological preconditions to halt further peat decay and CO₂ emissions.
- reported CO₂ and CH₄ emissions must be based on in-situ measurements, as modelling studies by their nature tend to reproduce reported data and their incorporation may produce redundancy.

Our literature survey added up to a total of 46 site-years. The reported emissions considered for our review are listed in the Appendix.

Results

Magnitude and interannual variation in CO₂ and CH₄ exchange after rewetting of a temperate fen

The rewetted fen used as an example case acted as a net CO₂ sink throughout the study period. Yet, NEE budgets varied substantially from -1,100 to -390 g CO₂ m⁻² yr⁻¹, which was primarily due to the high variation in its component flux R_{ECO} (Fig. 1a). R_{ECO} ranged from 1,900 to 2,710 g CO₂ m⁻² yr⁻¹, and its interannual variation could be explained almost entirely by the year-to-year fluctuation in the mean annual water level ($R^2 = 0.92$). According to this relationship, a 10 cm drop in mean annual water level increased the respiratory CO₂ loss by 307 ± 35 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ ($p < 0.001$, Table 1). GEP ranged from -3,190 to -2,790 g CO₂ m⁻² yr⁻¹, and its inter-annual variation was associated with the year-to-year fluctuation in vegetation development represented by EVI and a non-significant phenological effect: An increase in peak EVI by 0.1 increased the photosynthetic CO₂ uptake by 746 ± 322 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ ($p = 0.06$) and an earlier start of the growing season added another 8 ± 5 g CO₂ m⁻² per day ($p = 0.14$) to the GEP budget. Only half of the interannual variation in GEP could be explained by the linear combination of peak EVI and timing of the growing season start ($R^2 = 0.52$). The year-to-year variation in R_{ECO} was twice as high as that for GEP with a maximum range of 810 g CO₂ m⁻² compared to 400 g CO₂ m⁻² for GEP. Whilst no valid regression could be fitted between the annual sums of GEP and NEE ($R^2 = 0.02$), 74% of the inter-annual variation in NEE could be explained by R_{ECO}. Like for R_{ECO}, water level was also a major control for NEE: According to our statistical model, a 10 cm rise in mean annual water level increased the net CO₂ uptake by 251 ± 66 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ ($p < 0.01$, $R^2 = 0.71$, Table 1). In contrast, vegetation and phenology parameters had a negligible effect on NEE.

Figure 1 Annual budgets of CO₂ (a) and CH₄ (b) after rewetting of our case study site in 2010. The CO₂ exchange was measured as net ecosystem exchange (NEE) and further partitioned into its component fluxes gross ecosystem productivity (GEP) and ecosystem respiration (R_{Eco}). Fluxes were derived from the eddy covariance approach with the exception of CH₄ fluxes in 2010, which were measured with closed chambers (Hahn et al., 2015).

Table 1 Model results for the explanation of the inter-annual variation of fluxes in our rewetting case study site. The time period considered comprises stationary conditions during the post-rewetting period from 2010 to 2017 for net ecosystem exchange (NEE) and the component fluxes gross ecosystem productivity (GEP) and ecosystem respiration (R_{ECO}). The model period for CH₄ was restricted from 2011 to 2017 due to extraordinarily high emissions after vegetation dieback in the first year of rewetting (Hahn et al., 2015a). Models are either uni- or bivariate with water level, the start/end date of the growing season, or the yearly maximum of the enhanced vegetation index (EVI_{max}) as predictor variables. The interpretation of the fitted coefficients follows from the input variable units and sign convention and is described in the text.

Flux	Goodness of fit and model coefficients		
R_{ECO}	R^2 : 0.93		
	Intercept:	3,182±105	p<0.001
	Coef _{WaterLevel} :	-3,068±348	p<0.001
GEP	R^2 : 0.52		
	Intercept:	206±1,246	p: 0.88
	Coef _{EVI_{max}} :	7,455±3,218	p: 0.06
	Coef _{GrowSeasStart} :	8±5	p: 0.14
NEE	R^2 : 0.71		
	Intercept:	32±200	p: 0.88
	Coef _{WaterLevel} :	-2,508±662	p: 0.01
CH ₄	R^2 : 0.83		
	Intercept:	-298±104	p: 0.05
	Coef _{EVI_{max}} :	614±143	p: 0.01
	Coef _{GrowSeasEnd} :	0.23±0.16	p: 0.24

CH₄ emissions were by far highest (260 g m⁻² yr⁻¹) in 2010, the first year after rewetting, but decreased down to 44-75 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ in the following years (Fig. 1b). Since the high CH₄ emissions in 2010 presented a unique pulse confined to the first rewetting year (Hahn et al. 2015), the regression model to explain the inter-annual variation in CH₄ was set up only with the budgets from 2011-2017. Like for GEP, the inter-annual variation of these CH₄ budgets was associated mainly with vegetation development ($R^2=0.83$). There was also a small non-significant phenological effect, though the critical phenological stage for CH₄ concerned rather the end than the start of the season: according to the model, an increase in peak EVI by 0.1 increased CH₄ emissions by 61±14 g m⁻² (p=0.01) and every additional growing season day in autumn added 0.23±0.16 g CH₄ m⁻² to the annual budget (p=0.24).

Radiative forcing trajectory and evolving climate impact of rewetting a temperate fen

The RF dynamics modelled for the rewetted temperate fen used as an example case is based on the rates of net CO₂ uptake and CH₄ release measured in the first eight rewetting years, and the extrapolation of the emission behaviour observed at the 2nd year of rewetting into the future. The estimated long-term emission behaviour determined by the bootstrapping extrapolation approach is based on average fluxes of -640 g CO₂ and 66 g CH₄ m⁻² yr⁻¹ with 95% confidence intervals (CI₉₅) of [-499, -787], and [58, 74] g m⁻² yr⁻¹, respectively (Fig. 2a).

The persistent net uptake of 640 g CO₂ m⁻² causes a reduction of the atmospheric CO₂ inventory by 400 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ in the initial rewetting phase and by 140 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ at the end of the 1,000 year modelling period (Fig. 2b). The growing discrepancy between the amounts of CO₂ sequestered by the rewetted peatland and the concurrent reduction in atmospheric CO₂ is due to resolution processes from other Earth system C reservoirs that partly offset the effect of the biospheric CO₂ uptake and gain more weight over time. Given the radiative efficiency of CO₂, every kg of CO₂ removed from the atmosphere exerts a climate cooling of 1.8 fW m⁻² (Fig 2c).

Despite persistent CH₄ emissions of 66 g m⁻² yr⁻¹, the cumulative increase in the atmospheric CH₄ inventory is capped by the continued removal of atmospheric CH₄ through oxidation processes (Fig. 2a, b). A quasi-equilibrium between sustained gain and removal of atmospheric CH₄, (here defined as less than 1 g m⁻² increase in the atmospheric CH₄ inventory per year), is accomplished within 50 years after rewetting. Every kg of atmospheric CH₄ exerts a primary climate warming of 228 fW m⁻², which is further amplified by a factor of 1.65 through indirect effects of CH₄ levels on ozone and stratospheric water vapor. We also conservatively take into account the additional warming effect of CO₂, which becomes relevant when CH₄ produced from ancient peat carbon is subsequently oxidized.

The actual climate impact of peatland rewetting, expressed as net radiative forcing (NRF), results from the gross RF components of persistent net CO₂ uptake and CH₄ release. At the beginning of rewetting, our case site acts as an NRF source, as the climate warming effect of CH₄ emissions cannot yet be outweighed by concurrent net CO₂ uptake. This early post-rewetting phase is characterized by a steady increase in the atmospheric CH₄ inventory and a concurrent rise in NRF up to a peak of 151 fW m⁻² (CI₉₅ [127, 179]). With increasing rewetting age and advancing removal of atmospheric CO₂, the NRF steadily decreases, eventually hitting zero within a switchover time of 650 years (CI₉₅ [367, 1,418]) under the given assumptions. During this period, the rewetted peatland releases GHG equivalent to 47,800 fW m⁻² of heat (CI₉₅ [24,000, 116,600]). However, the climate pay-off time, i.e., the time required for the rewetting measure to become climatically beneficial compared to a reference scenario of ongoing drainage, is already reached within 30 years (CI₉₅ [25, 37]).

Figure 2 Concurrent CH₄ release and net CO₂ uptake and the course of the radiative forcing (RF) trajectory evolving after peatland rewetting: **(a)** CO₂ and CH₄ emissions observed and extrapolated in a rewetted temperate fen; **(b)** the resulting atmospheric inventory; and **(c)** gross and net RF components. The extrapolation of fluxes over time is based on the bootstrapped means of observed fluxes (CO₂: $-640 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, 95% confidence interval: $[-499, -787]$; CH₄: $66 \text{ g m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, 95% confidence interval: $[58, 74]$). Dashed lines represent the uncertainty arising from the 95% confidence intervals of the bootstrapped flux means. As the atmospheric inventories of CO₂ and CH₄ differ by almost three orders of magnitude, the inset in 3b gives a more detailed picture for the evolution of atmospheric CH₄ during the first 250 rewetting years. The net RF of rewetting results from the gross RF components of net CO₂ uptake and CH₄ release **(c)**. Here, the switch over time marks the intercept of the net RF trajectory with the x axis, and indicates the onset of the peatland's climate cooling effect after the start of rewetting. We compared the climate impact of rewetting with a drainage scenario using emission factors obtained from Tiemeyer et al. (2020). The pay-off time marks the intersection of both RF trajectories and corresponds with the time when rewetting becomes climatically beneficial to drainage.

Reviewing the climate impact of peatland rewetting

Due to the large variation in peatland emissions in combination with a limited sample size ($n=46$), we constrained our assessment to simple univariate linear models to estimate effect sizes and/or t-tests to derive group-differences. We found the following criteria that affect the emission behaviour of a rewetted peatland:

- **Hydrology:** Post-rewetting water levels below surface (i.e. MAWL < 0) increase the risk to maintain net sources for CO₂ (mean: 41 ± 151 g CO₂-C m⁻² yr⁻¹), at commonly low CH₄ emissions (16 ± 23 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹). Rewetting with MAWL > 0 , in turn, is more likely to create net CO₂ sinks (mean: -109 ± 252 g CO₂-C m⁻² yr⁻¹), but comes at the cost of higher CH₄ emissions (55 ± 93 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹). Despite the high variation in post-rewetting emission behaviour in particular for MAWLs > 0 , the effect of water level is significant at $p < 0.05$ for CO₂ and at $p < 0.01$ for CH₄.
- **Peatland type:** CO₂ and CH₄ emissions for rewetted fens vary widely. Yet, fens are more likely to become net CO₂ sinks than bogs (-75 ± 257 and 23 ± 80 g CO₂-C m⁻² yr⁻¹, respectively, $p=0.05$). Moreover, fens are likely to emit higher amounts of CH₄ than bogs (50 ± 72 and 4 ± 3 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹, respectively, $p=0.001$).
- **Land-use history:** Former peat extraction sites are more likely to remain net CO₂ sources and, in turn, have lower CH₄ emissions after rewetting. The emission ranges of both, CO₂ and CH₄, are comparatively well constrained with 34 ± 81 g CO₂-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ and 4 ± 4 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹, respectively. Rewetting of sites that have been drained for agriculture is more likely to create net CO₂ sinks (-73 ± 250 g CO₂-C m⁻² yr⁻¹), but risks higher CH₄ emissions (71 ± 47 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹). The difference between both land use categories is significant at $p < 0.05$ for CO₂ and $p < 0.01$ for CH₄. We could not find any significant differences between peatlands that had been drained for crop farming or grassland use.
- **Climate Zone:** Rewetted peatlands in boreal and oceanic climates are more likely to remain net CO₂ sources (17 ± 52 , and 75 ± 112 g CO₂-C m⁻² yr⁻¹, respectively), whereas rewetting in temperate and subtropical climates is more likely to create net CO₂ sinks (-65 ± 241 and -240 ± 250 g CO₂-C m⁻² yr⁻¹, respectively). The effect of the climate zone is significant at $p < 0.05$. Post-rewetting CH₄ emissions are lowest in boreal peatlands (4 ± 4 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹). There is no significant difference in CH₄ emissions from rewetted peatlands in other climatic zones (Oceanic: 30 ± 29 , Temperate: 46 ± 86 , Subtropical: 44 ± 8 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹, respectively).

Peak NRF, total NRF and switch over time as key metrics to assess the climate impact of rewetting are only defined for cases in which the peatland turns to a net C sink after rewetting, which applied to 20 out of 46 site-years in our literature review. 80% of these cases constitute fens rewetted after agricultural use with a MAWL of 15 ± 30 cm above ground. Further, as we base our assessment of pay-off time on

a reference scenario of a drained fen grassland, pay-off time is only estimated for studies from temperate peatlands under former grassland use which comprises 16 site-years and includes both, net CO₂ sinks and sources. Given the low sample size, we constrained our assessment to simple vote counts.

In our literature survey, peak NRF exceeded 100 fW m⁻² only in 3 out of 20 incidences, constituting fens with high rewetting water levels and CH₄ emissions > 50 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ (Fig. 3a). Provided that the peatland becomes a net C sink after rewetting, the maximum warming effect is essentially determined by the CH₄ emissions, while the magnitude of the CO₂ sink strength is largely irrelevant. The study of Augustin et al. (2008) from a rewetted fen stands out with particularly high CH₄ emissions of 190 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ and simultaneously high net CO₂ uptake rates of 500 g CO₂-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ observed in the year 2005. Here, the total NRF is 600 fW m⁻².

The total RF, i.e. the total warming exerted by rewetting before the peatland turns to a net RF sink, is extremely variable and changes by several orders of magnitude even with small variations in emission behaviour (Fig. 3b). Valid predictions of the total warming exerted through rewetting are, thus, difficult to make. From our literature survey the following can be stated as a rough estimate: four incidences emit GHGs equivalent to less than 100 fW m⁻² until they eventually turn into net CO₂ sinks. Another three incidences emit GHGs equivalent to less than 1,000 fW m⁻², and the majority of incidences emit GHGs equivalent of up to 10,000 fW m⁻².

The switchover time, i.e., the time period elapsed since rewetting when the peatland eventually exerts a net cooling effect, is exponentially related to the ratio between CH₄ release and net CO₂ uptake. In practice, short switchover times < 25 years can only be reached at CH₄ emissions < 15 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹, though these need to be offset by net CO₂ uptake > 500 g CO₂-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ as in (Schrier-Uijl et al., 2014) (Fig. 3c). In our literature survey, short switchover times < 25 years occurred in three out of 20 incidences, all of which constitute observations from fens rewetted after agricultural use. Provided that rewetting can re-establish the peatland net C sink function, most cases reach climate neutrality within 200 years. Yet, under very high CH₄ emissions as reported by Augustin et al. (2008), switchover time could even exceed 1,000 years.

The pay-off time is here defined as the amount of time it takes for rewetting to become climatically beneficial compared to a reference scenario of ongoing drainage. Under the chosen drainage emission factors, the pay-off time remains zero (i.e., instant climate benefits) up to CH₄ emission levels of 35 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ (Fig. 3d). This applies even if the rewetted peatland remains a net CO₂ source with emissions up to 200 g CO₂-C m⁻² yr⁻¹. At moderate emission levels of 55 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹, climate benefits can still be reached within 25 years after rewetting. In our literature survey, half of the incidences reached immediate climate benefits after rewetting. In one case it took four years, and in four other cases 10-30 years to become climatically beneficial compared to the ongoing drainage scenario. For CH₄ emissions > 170 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ as reported in Augustin et al. (2008) in the

observation years 2005 and 2007, the pay-off time extends to 150 years at minimum, and may even double if the net CO₂ sink is diminished from -500 to 10 g CO₂-C m⁻² yr⁻¹.

Figure 3 Maps of key metrics to assess the climate impact of peatland rewetting in relation to annual sums of net CO₂ uptake and CH₄ release obtained from a literature survey. Metrics were derived from distinct features of the net radiative forcing (NRF) trajectory as computed with atmospheric perturbation modelling. **4a:** Peak NRF constitutes the maximum climate warming exerted during the rewetting phase before the decline of NRF sets in. **4b:** the total NRF exerted through peatland rewetting presents the heating effect accumulated during the rewetting phase until the peatland eventually reaches climate neutrality. **4c:** the switchover time marks the time when the NRF trajectory approaches zero and the peatland becomes climatically neutral. **4d:** the climate pay-off time, i.e., the time when rewetting becomes climatically beneficial compared to intensive grassland utilization (Tiemeyer et al., 2020) as reference scenario for a business-as-usual land use. Data points present assessment metrics derived from reported rewetting cases. Symbols code previous land use with crosses representing peatlands rewetted after agricultural use (crops and grassland) and filled circles representing former peat extraction sites. Grey scale levels present a range in mean annual water level (MAWL) with MAWLs 10-30 cm below ground in light grey, MAWLs from 10 cm below to 10 cm above ground in medium grey and MAWLs higher than 10 cm above ground in dark grey.

Discussion

Magnitude and interannual variation in CO₂ and CH₄ exchange after rewetting of a temperate fen

The rewetted peatland functioned as a substantial net CO₂ sink from the onset of rewetting, i.e., photosynthetic CO₂ sequestration continuously exceeded the composite CO₂ release from autotrophic respiration and the heterotrophic decomposition of recent litter and old peat. The component fluxes R_{ECO} and GEP were of significant magnitude, indicating considerable productivity of the system with substantial rates of biomass accumulation and C turnover (Franz et al., 2016; Koebisch et al., 2013) as it is common for many fens with a drainage-rewetting land use history (Zak & Gelbrecht, 2007). The interannual variation in R_{ECO} was tightly coupled to the year-to-year fluctuation in water level and therefore mainly controlled by the redox potential and its regulatory effect on organic matter degradation processes. In turn, only half of the year-to-year differences in GEP as a quantity for the photosynthetic uptake of CO₂, could be explained by vegetation dynamics, here represented by the EVI. Overall, the interannual variation of net CO₂ uptake was controlled less by vegetation dynamics transmitted through GEP than by R_{ECO} and its sensitive responses to water levels. The role of water level as a key control suggests that even small variations in the hydrological regime, whether due to climatic phenomena or due to management interventions, could cause significant changes in the CO₂ budget of peatlands (see also Wilson, Blain, et al., 2016).

The exceptionally high CH₄ emissions of 260 g CH₄ m⁻² yr⁻¹ in the first rewetting year were fuelled by the die-back of large portions of the established vegetation and the resulting provision of fresh organic matter for methanogenesis (Hahn et al., 2015). At our case study site, rewetting re-established predominantly anaerobic conditions combined with a large supply of labile C compounds and thereby set the ground for a thriving methanogenic community and intensive methane production (Koebisch et al., 2019; Wen et al., 2018). In the following years, CH₄ emissions settled down but still exceeded the annual totals of most temperate wetlands (typically < 30 g CH₄ m⁻² yr⁻¹, (Hemes et al., 2018)). In contrast to many studies that report water level as a critical control for CH₄ emissions, the year-to-year variation of CH₄ fluxes in our study case was largely driven by the vegetation state represented by EVI. EVI in its function as a satellite-derived proxy for vegetation spread and vitality, could also indicate the promoting effect of plant-mediated gas transport and/or the resupply of fresh organic matter through root exudation for ecosystem-scale CH₄ exchange (Sebacher et al., 1985). Thus, water level fluctuations are likely irrelevant provided the system remains predominantly inundated.

Climate impact of rewetting a temperate fen

The net RF trajectory and the evolving climate impact characteristic for peatland rewetting correspond to that of newly formed natural peatlands that cannot build on a prolonged history of continuous C accumulation (Frolking et al., 2006). In its initial state, peatland rewetting, like the formation of new peatlands, exhibits a period of net warming, until the RF of the CH₄ accumulating in the atmosphere is compensated by ongoing net CO₂ removal. The switchover time, i.e. the duration it takes for peatland rewetting to establish net cooling, is highly sensitive to the ratio between CH₄ release and net CO₂ uptake (Frolking et al., 2006). As demonstrated by the large confidence interval estimated for the switchover time of our case study site (CI₉₅ [367, 1,418]), this metric cannot be precisely estimated given the high variation inherent to peatland GHG exchange. Likewise, total RF, i.e., the heat energy emitted until switchover time is reached, is highly uncertain with a CI₉₅ range of 24,000 to 116,600 fW m⁻². Time horizons of centuries to millennia are certainly far beyond relevant for political actions. However, rewetting of our case study site turned out to be climatically beneficial after only 30 years when compared with EF of continued drainage as the alternative land use scenario. The timing of climate benefits is comparatively well constrained (CI₉₅ [25, 37]) to support informed land use decisions.

While the long-term development of any ecosystem over time scales of centuries to millennia is hardly predictable, the geochemical basis for the climate impact as it emerges from the simultaneous net CO₂ uptake and CH₄ release and the gasses' depletion processes in the atmosphere is comparatively well constrained. The resulting climate effect dynamics are described by the characteristic shape of the RF trajectory, which is, to a certain extent, modulated by the variation in peatland emission behaviour. Here, we assess the climate impact of peatland rewetting at our case study site under the assumption that the mean emission behaviour observed in 2010-2017 will remain constant. Indeed, the peatland under study was hit by several disruptions after the seven years had elapsed: in 2018, the rewetted fen experienced a substantial drought (Beyer et al., 2021; Koebisch et al., 2020), and in the following year, brackish water intrusion altered the pore water biogeochemistry significantly (Gutekunst et al., 2022). The way we implemented uncertainty in our assessment, is based on a considerable range of variation obtained from a 7-year steady-state observation period (-499 to -787 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ for CO₂, and 58 to 74 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ for CH₄). Given the sustained reduction in CH₄ emissions after the drought year 2018 (Koebisch et al., 2020), the extrapolation of the high CH₄ emissions over several centuries renders our estimation rather conservative. A substantial decrease of high CH₄ emissions > 100 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ has also been documented for another temperate fen rewetted after grassland use (Antonijević et al., 2023; Augustin & Chojnicki, 2008; Franz et al., 2016; Koebisch et al., 2020), so that climate mitigation could still be reached within 25-35 years. We think that scenarios representing different trajectories of peatland evolution and their implications for the radiative forcing need to be inferred from peatland development

models that couple mechanical, ecological, and hydrological processes over longer time scales (Mahdiyasa et al., 2022). Yet, such complex ecosystem models are beyond the scope of this study.

Whilst the uncertainty inherent to climate effect predictions needs to be taken into account, it must not stand in the way of informed land use decisions. This holds in particular as climate mitigation in relation to ongoing drainage can be reached in well-constrained time periods of a few decades, which makes it less susceptible to uncertainties associated with long-term peatland development.

Literature review: Peatland rewetting as a climate protection measure

As CH₄ emissions and net CO₂ uptake of rewetted peatlands can vary considerably from site to site, and also over time from year to year, the climate impacts of peatland rewetting are highly diverse. As a consequence, the intended climate targets can be subject to large uncertainty as the evolution of the rewetted peatland and its emission behaviour are hard to predict. In particular, it remains vague whether a peatland can reach climate neutrality, and subsequently, re-establish its natural cooling function within relevant time periods: Not even half of the cases considered in our review constitute net C sinks as a prerequisite criterion to reach climate neutrality. Among those cases, the switchover time varies by several orders of magnitude from a few decades, if low CH₄ emissions coincide with high net CO₂ uptake (Schrier-Uijl et al., 2014), to more than 1,000 years at high CH₄ emissions and low net CO₂ sequestration (Augustin & Chojnicki, 2008). Most rewetted peatlands that constitute net C sinks achieve climate neutrality within 200 years, though this estimate is prone to high uncertainty.

According to our literature review, the problem of net C sources persisting after rewetting is not primarily due to high CH₄ emissions, but rather to the lack of an adequate net CO₂ sink. This is particularly true for rewetted bogs: 9 out of 14 cases feature well-constrained CH₄ emissions below 7 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹, but remain a net CO₂ source and are therefore unlikely to reach climate neutrality in foreseeable time periods. This is probably due to the low productivity and/or slow vegetation establishment typical of these peatland types, which may partly be related to the high latitude location of many bogs (D'Acunha et al., 2019; Strack & Zuback, 2013). In particular, in previous peat extraction sites, active moss planting measures can promote the establishment of a net CO₂ sink (Nugent et al., 2018). Likewise, an increase in vegetation cover can increase GEP in rewetted fens (Zhou et al., 2023), and thus bring climate neutrality within reach. Natural vegetation spread after rewetting does not necessarily have to be linear, but can also be event-driven, e.g. through rapid expansion boosts after temporary drought (Koebsch et al., 2020). Another reason for peatlands remaining net C sources after rewetting is the substantial lateral imports of allochthonous C. Whilst this may be a characteristic process in riverine fens, it remains a problem in climate assessments based on confined ecosystem-scale boundaries.

Before reaching switchover time, peatland rewetting commonly exerts a temporary warming effect, described through the peak NRF in our study. Our analysis reveals that the peak NRF is limited to 100 fW m⁻² for most rewetting cases. Most importantly, however, in cases where rewetting does not pay off immediately (pay-off time > 0), the NRF caused by rewetting is only slightly higher than the NRF caused by ongoing drainage. We therefore assume that even rewetting projects with an unfavourable outcome (high CH₄ emissions) do not contradict the requirement to reduce emissions as quickly as possible. In contrast: Günther et al. (2020) advocate for immediate action so that the mid-term mitigation effects achievable through peatland rewetting can contribute to attenuating the global emission peak.

Climate benefits for fen rewetting compared to grassland use as described by the pay-off time, could be achieved immediately in half of the cases studied. Such climate benefits occur primarily as rewetting reduces the net CO₂ emissions prevalent under drainage. The relationship between pay-off time and peatland emission behaviour is described by two basic features:

1. Below a certain CH₄ emission limit, pay-off time is decoupled from CH₄ emission levels and rewetting achieves instant climate benefits. Such a decoupling appears if the initial slope of the rewetting net RF trajectory is flatter than that of the drainage trajectory, so that the two curves do not intersect. In our study, focussing on the pay-off time for the rewetting of temperate fens after grassland use with net CO₂ emissions of 200 g CO₂-C m⁻² yr⁻¹, instant climate benefits are guaranteed up to CH₄ emission limits of 35 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ (Fig. 3a).
2. If CH₄ emissions exceed the decoupling limit, pay-off time increases with CH₄ emissions, whereby the slope of this increase is modulated by CO₂ savings compared to drainage. This suggests that even a moderate reduction in net CO₂ emissions through rewetting can yield rapid climate benefits without an imperative conversion of the peatland from a net CO₂ source to a net CO₂ sink. CH₄ emission levels above a certain limit, however, may substantially extend pay-off times. Yet, in the majority of cases, peatland rewetting can generate climate benefits in no more than 20-30 years with a moderate level of uncertainty.

Although we illustrated these RF relationships particularly for the case of temperate fen rewetting after grassland use, analogous patterns likely hold for other peatland types and land use histories.

A temporary increase in climate warming evolving from resumed CH₄ emissions is often regarded as an adverse side effect of rewetting and can dominate the discussion of the efficacy of peatland rewetting as a climate protection measure (Hemes et al., 2018; Taillardat et al., 2020). Median CH₄ emissions in our review amount to 2.2 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ for rewetted bogs, and 31.5 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ for rewetted fens, respectively. Though the selection criteria for our literature review covered only a subset of the existing literature, it indicates that extraordinarily high CH₄ emissions after rewetting are not the common case, but may gain a disproportionately high impact if statistics utilized in reviews base on average CH₄ emissions. Above, we have discussed that the achievement of climate protection goals for

many rewetted bogs is prevented by the lack of an adequate net CO₂ sink rather than by high CH₄ emissions. Extraordinarily high CH₄ emissions are mostly confined to temperate fens formerly drained for agriculture and subsequently rewetted by flooding. Such CH₄ emission levels could substantially compromise some of the climate protection goals of peatland rewetting, but are likely a transitory effect. Hence, even for these cases, there is a realistic chance that climate benefits compared with drainage can still be achieved within societally-relevant time periods of a few decades. Under common fen emission levels of 31.5 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹, climate benefits can be reached instantaneously.

Conclusions

The climate impact of peatland rewetting is multi-faceted. Hence, the assessment of the efficacy of peatland rewetting as a climate protection measure strongly depends on the climate protection aspect to be prioritized and results in partly conflicting management strategies:

- To harness the climate cooling function of peatlands in relevant time scales requires the conversion from a net CO₂ source to a net CO₂ sink, while at the same time keeping CH₄ emissions low. The rapid establishment of greenhouse gas sinks over societal-relevant time periods of no more than 20-30 years is only rarely possible. Based on our assessment, the chances seem higher in rewetted fens, where large plant productivity is more likely to offset the warming effect of CH₄ emissions up to 15 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹.
- To alleviate the initial warming pulse triggered through peatland rewetting, priority must be given to reducing CH₄ emissions. Our literature review suggests that CH₄ emissions in rewetted bogs are lower than in rewetted fens (4±3 and 50±72 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ respectively). However, given the low productivity of bogs, and the slow natural vegetation development, particularly in previous peat extraction sites, this advantage can come at the price of persistent net CO₂ emissions i.e., a timely cooling effect may not be foreseeable for most of these peatlands. Similarly, rewetting with a mean annual water table below the surface can reduce CH₄ emissions from 55±93 to 16±23 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ across all peatland types, but again at the risk that net CO₂ emissions may persist in the future.
- To quickly achieve climate benefits compared to continued drainage, net CO₂ emissions must be reduced in the first instance, with a secondary focus on lowered CH₄ emissions. For the rewetted temperate fens previously used as grassland that we addressed in this study, instant climate benefits are primarily achieved through CO₂ savings in comparison to drainage, even if CO₂ emissions cannot be completely stopped. Nevertheless, reducing CH₄ emissions at least to levels below 55 g CH₄-C m⁻² yr⁻¹ is required to reach climate benefits within a few years to decades.

In practice, the implementation of peatland rewetting is commonly limited by factual constraints, in particular, the availability of land suitable for rewetting and the prevailing hydrological conditions. In this context, the debate about the maximum possible exploitation potential of peatland rewetting might often appear academic.

We suggest assessing the climate impact of peatland rewetting based on the climate pay-off time, and the CO₂-equivalents saved from drainage over an appropriate reference period as complementary metrics to the global warming potential (GWP). The suggested metrics indicate whether climate mitigation can be achieved in societal-relevant time periods with an acceptable level of uncertainty. Both metrics are related to a business-as-usual scenario and thereby reflect the consideration process between two alternative land use forms that land managers and decision-makers actually encounter in practice. In line with reporting activities for the LULUCF sector, the savings in CO₂-equivalents generated by rewetting could be based on a common 100-year reference period. However, also shorter time periods such as 25 years are conceivable, as these are more geared towards the targets of the Paris Agreement to reach net zero by 2050.

Our assessment based on the pay-off time for temperate fens previously drained for grassland use indicates that rewetting can achieve instant climate benefits from the reduction of CO₂ emissions in comparison to drainage. Timely climate benefits can be achieved even if peatland rewetting does not lead to optimal results, i.e. the net CO₂ source may not be completely shut down and/or CH₄ is emitted at levels typical for rewetting. The potential of peatland rewetting as a climate protection measure is thus not primarily the creation of GHG sinks, but peatland rewetting can make an important contribution to reducing existing CO₂ sources in the land use sector in a timely manner. Measures to reduce CH₄ emissions and/or create net CO₂ sinks can additionally improve the climate efficacy of rewetting. Though, in practice, these benefits must be weighed against the financial and CO₂ costs of the required measures such as biomass harvesting, topsoil removal, active introduction of target vegetation and active water level management.

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